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Manufacturing technology problems

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$$\Phi_1 = \frac{1}{4.44fW_{11}} U_1$$

$$\Phi_{\sigma 1} = \frac{L_{\sigma 1.8} I_1}{W_{11}}$$

The main and shunt magnetic fluxes cross the gauge lobes, creating an EMF in the coil, and we can look at its formula to find E_1 .

$$E_1 = \sqrt{2}\pi f w_{11} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}\pi f w_1} (I_1 - Z_1 I_1) = \frac{U_1 - Z_1 I_1}{k_w}$$

In the figure below, we can see the situation where we obtained the output signal of our sensing element when changing the loads on phases 1 and 3 of our 250 kVA asynchronous motor under modern laboratory conditions.

Figure 2

In the picture, we can see the laboratory stand and measuring equipment of a consumer asynchronous motor device from an alternative energy store.

In our experimental current transformer, the primary current changes and the current control of the induction motor are generated by the magnetic flux of the stator coils based on the magnetic flux, two independent sense coil loops control the stray magnetic flux between the phases through the controller. contacts. They are connected separately, and as a result, below we can see the static characteristic of the output voltage of the measuring sensitive loops.

In our experimental current transformer, the primary current changes and the current control of the induction motor are generated from the magnetic flux of the stator coils based on the magnetic flux, two independent sense coil loops control the stray magnetic flux between the phases through the controller contacts. . are connected separately and as a result below we can see the static characteristic of the output voltage of the measuring sensitive loops.

Results. We can see the theoretical form of the static description of the output currents and the output signal of the induction motor obtained in the experiment.

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